

FIBRE ORIENTATION EFFECTS ON THE TENSILE PROPERTIES OF BIAXIAL CARBON/EPOXY NCF COMPOSITES

K. Vallons, I. Duque, S. V. Lomov and I. Verpoest
Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44 bus 2450, 3001 Leuven, Belgium
Katleen.vallons@mtm.kuleuven.be

SUMMARY

In this work, the effect of fibre orientation on the tensile properties of a cross-ply carbon/epoxy NCF composite was studied. Both static and dynamic properties were investigated for several sample orientations. On 5° oriented samples the influence of the sample width was studied.

Keywords: Non crimp fabric composites, NCF, mechanical properties, fibre orientation, fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Non crimp fabric composites (NCFC) are very promising materials, as they combine mechanical properties close to those of UD laminates with the possibility for relatively easy and cost-effective production methods. However, certain artefacts, e.g. resin rich zones, exist in these composites, which may have an influence on the properties. It is therefore important to systematically characterise the behaviour of these materials, and to investigate if, and if so to what degree, their performance differs from that of UD laminates or woven fabric composites.

In large-scale composite structures with complex shapes, the fibre orientation spatially varies. This implies that composite elements are locally subjected to a certain degree of off-axis loading. It is therefore necessary to know the behaviour of these materials when they are subjected to such loading cases. Although limited work is available on the off-axis properties of cross-ply or textile composites, the properties of unidirectional composites under off-axis loading conditions are relatively well known.

Using the classical laminate theory (CLT), the elastic constants for a single off-axis unidirectional ply can be easily predicted. The stiffness of a multidirectional UD laminate in any direction can also be predicted. Through the use of a suitable failure criterion, the initiation of damage in such a composite can be calculated when it is loaded in a certain direction.

The prediction of the behaviour of off-axis UD laminae and laminates in fatigue, however, is more difficult. Several models have been developed in the past for this purpose, e.g. in [1]. Often, it is attempted to define one or more parameters that allow for the construction of a master fatigue life curve, in which the fibre orientation

influence is effectively eliminated. For example, Varvani-Farahani et al. [2] recently developed an energy-based fatigue damage parameter for off-axis unidirectional composites, that results in a very high degree of correlation of the fatigue data.

An interesting series of studies on the dependence of the static and fatigue properties of different types of composite materials on the off-axis angle was reported on by Kawai et al. [3-5]. In [3], they investigated the off-axis tensile-tensile fatigue behaviour of UD carbon fibre reinforced composites at room temperature, and at 100° C. They determined the tensile strength and fatigue life for samples with an orientation θ of 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45 and 90°. They found a very good agreement between their results and the predictions of the Tsai-Hill criterion. From the tensile-tensile fatigue tests, they concluded that the off-axis fatigue life curves are approximately described by straight lines, irrespective of the fibre orientation. After normalising the fatigue life curves using the corresponding off-axis static strength, the different curves all fell within a narrow scatter band. In [4, 5], they found very similar behaviour for a cross-ply laminate and a plain woven fabric composite.

The present study was aimed at characterising the off-axis tensile behaviour of non crimp fabric composites. In a first part, the sensitivity of the NCFC material to small misorientations with respect to the intended loading direction was investigated. Such a small misorientation of a few degrees could for example originate from a lack of precision during the production phase. The static and dynamic tensile properties of samples with a deliberate misorientation of 5° were determined and the influence of the width of the test samples on the results was assessed. In a second part, the strength, stiffness and damage initiation in samples with larger off-axis orientations were studied and compared to the properties of on-axis samples. The fatigue life curves for the different testing directions were constructed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The non crimp fabric (NCF) used for this work is a chain stitched biaxial ($\pm 45^\circ$) carbon fibre NCF with an areal weight of 540 g/m². Both a ($+45^\circ, -45^\circ$) and a ($-45^\circ, +45^\circ$) fabric were used, to allow for the production of fully symmetric composite plates. The fabric is supplied prelaminated with an epoxy resin layer. Composite plates were produced by means of a modified RFI process. In a first step, prepreg layers were produced from the prelaminated fabric. In the second step, several prepreg layers were stacked to obtain a composite with a fibre volume fraction of about 57 %. In both steps, a vacuum was applied for 15 minutes at room temperature to debulk. The assembly (see figure 1) was placed in an oven and the time-temperature cycles shown in table 1 were applied, while maintaining the vacuum. The produced plates have a thickness of about 2.1mm and a biaxial lay up: $[+45, -45, +45, -45]_s$.

Samples were cut with different orientations (0°, 5°, 15°, 30°, and 45°) compared to the orientation of one of the two fibre directions. Glass fibre/epoxy endtabs with a thickness of 4 mm were glued to the ends of all samples, in such a way that the gauge length of the samples was 150 mm. Static tensile tests on 25 mm or 50 mm wide samples were done on an Instron 4505 hydraulic machine with a load cell of 100 kN. A crosshead displacement speed of 1 mm/min was used. Tests on wider samples were done on a MFL machine with a 2500 kN load cell. The stiffness was monitored with an

extensometer or by strain mapping. Tensile-tensile fatigue tests on the 25 mm and 50 mm wide samples were done in load-control mode on a Schenck hydraulic machine with a scalable load cell of 160 kN. A test frequency of 6 Hz and an R-ratio of 0.1 were used. For the 90 mm wide samples, the MFL machine was used, with a frequency of 2.5 Hz.

Figure 1: The set-up used for the composite production

Table 1: Processing conditions for the composite production

Step	Time (min)	Temp. (°C)	Vacuum (MPa)
1	15	20	-0.095
	5	90	-0.095
2	15	20	-0.095
	60	90	-0.095
	90	130	-0.095

RESULTS

Sensitivity to small misorientations

In table 2, the static strength and stiffness of the 5° off-axis samples are listed for different specimen widths. The results for the on-axis (0°) samples are also shown in the table. If the test results for the 25 mm wide 5° samples are compared to the 0° samples, it is clear that the misalignment has an influence on both the stiffness and strength of the material. A stiffness decrease of about 10 % was observed, while the strength is reduced by almost 50 %.

Table 2: Results of the static tensile tests 5° off-axis samples compared to the results for the on-axis samples.

	0°	5° off-axis		
	25	25	50	90
Sample width (mm)	25	25	50	90
% of bridging fibres	100	48	74	85
Stiffness (GPa)	68 ± 3	62 ± 2	/	/
Strength (MPa)	992 ± 25	528 ± 21	666 ± 30	697 ± 28

Figure 2: Illustration of the influence of the sample width on the proportion of fibres running from one end tab to the other.

Because only part of the 5° fibres bridge the gauge length between the endtabs (see figure 2), the width of the sample could have a significant influence on the measured strength. Therefore, tests were repeated with 50 mm and 90 mm wide samples with the same gauge length. The results can also be seen in table 2. An increase in strength was indeed noted for the wider samples. By linear extrapolation of these results, to a proportion of bridging fibres of 100 %, the strength of a sample with an infinite width can be estimated to be 774 MPa (see figure 3). This is a decrease in strength of 22 % compared to the 0° oriented samples.

Figure 3: Determination of the strength of a 5° off-axis sample with infinite width.

In figure 4, the fatigue life curve for the 0° oriented samples is shown, together with the fatigue results for the 5° off-axis samples with the different widths. If the results for the 25 mm wide samples are considered, it could be concluded that the relatively small misorientation of 5° causes a drastic decrease in fatigue life, comparable to the decrease in static strength. Also for the fatigue tests, however, an important influence of the

sample width was noted. For the 50 mm samples as well as for the 90 mm samples, only one test sample broke before the test was stopped for time-limiting reasons.

From the increase in strength found in the static tests for the wider samples, it could be expected that the fatigue life would also be increased, proportional to the increase in sample width. A higher fatigue life was indeed noticed for the wider samples. It is very remarkable however, that it seems that for wider samples, the curve becomes less steep. The data point for the 90 mm sample that broke at about 10^6 cycles corresponds to a fatigue stress that is only slightly lower than the static strength for this sample type. Moreover, this data point is also very close to the scatter band of the fatigue life for the on-axis samples at this fatigue stress. Since it is highly unlikely that the two curves will eventually cross each other, it can be expected that for higher fatigue lives, the results for the 0° on-axis direction and for wide 5° off-axis samples will coincide. However, since only one data point is available, no definitive conclusions can be reached. It can only be stated that based on the present results, the influence of the 5° misalignment on the fatigue behaviour of the NCFC material under study seems much less important than the influence on the static tensile strength.

Figure 4: The fatigue life results for the different widths of the 5° off-axis samples, compared to the results for the 0° on-axis samples.

Larger off-axis orientations

Static tensile tests have been done for samples with an orientation of 15° , 30° and 45° compared to the 0° on-axis direction. All tested samples had a width of 25 mm. Figure 5 and table 3 show the results obtained from the static tensile tests in the different directions, compared to those for the 0° and 5° samples, as discussed above. For the 5° samples, also the estimated strength for an infinitely wide laminate is shown in the

graph. Estimations of the stiffness and damage initiation using the Composite Star[®] program, based on the CLT, have also been included.

Figure 5: Tensile test results for the different laminate orientation angles. (a) stiffness, compared to the theoretical values, (b) stress at damage initiation, and (c) strength.

Table 3: Static tensile test results for the different laminate orientation angles, and the corresponding predictions from the CLT.

Orientation	Stiffness (GPa)		Damage initiation stress (MPa)		Strength (MPa)
	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.	Pred.	Exp.
0°	68±3	69,5	270±3	248	992±25
5°	62±2	64	264±14	236	774
15°	37±3	39,9	222±7	187	234±3
30°	17±2	21,5	123±3	143	129±1
45°	16±1	17,5	97±5	137	121±2

The observed stiffness evolution (see figure 5 (a)) as a function of the fibre orientation angle corresponds very well to the evolution predicted by the classical laminate theory. A moderate decrease in modulus was found for a misalignment of 5°. For larger off-axis angles, the stiffness is reduced more. Between the stiffness of the 30° and 45° samples, the difference is very small.

A similar trend is seen for the stress at damage initiation and the static tensile strength, as shown in figure 5 (b) and (c), although the decrease in strength for the 15° samples is larger than what might be expected based on the stiffness decrease. It is possible that also for this case, a width-effect exists, similar to that in 5° oriented samples. A mismatch of about 10-15 % was found between the predicted first ply failure and the measured damage initiation stress, except for the 45° oriented samples, where the deviation is much larger, and the predicted value is even larger than the experimentally observed strength. The overestimation might be due to the non-linear behaviour of the matrix material, which is not taken into account in the predictions.

From the results of the fatigue tests on the different types of samples, the fatigue life curves for the different orientations were constructed. They are shown in figure 6. This graph also shows the results for the 0° direction, as well as the results for the 5° off-axis samples with the three different widths. It is possible that a similar width-effect as that for the 5° samples exists for some of the other orientations used in this paragraph (15°, and possibly 30°).

From the figure, it can be concluded that the fatigue strength indeed shows a similar behaviour as the static strength for varying orientation of the laminate. A sharp decrease in strength was observed when the off-axis orientation varies from 0° to 15°. After that, the decrease is much smaller. The curves for the 15°, 30° and 45° are very close together, again reflecting the results from the static tests, which were also very close together for these samples.

Figure 7 shows the normalised fatigue life curves for the different fibre orientations. Because of the observed width-effect, the results for the 5° off-axis samples have been omitted. Normalisation was done with respect to the obtained static strength, as it was done by Kawai et al. in [3-5]. It can be seen from the graph that this simple normalisation procedure effectively removes the fibre orientation dependence of the fatigue life. All the results are within one scatter band. This 'master curve' allows for a rudimentary estimation of the fatigue life for a certain orientation, even if only the static strength for this case is known.

Figure 7 also shows the probability intervals (10^{-6} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-2}) for the obtained master curve. These intervals are relatively wide, and indicate that the results obtained by means of this master curve must be used with care: from the present data, the predicted fatigue life might, with a relatively high probability, deviate several orders of magnitude from the fatigue life in an individual experiment.

Figure 6: Fatigue life curves for the different orientations. For the 5° tests, the results for the three sample widths are shown. the width of all other sample types was 25 mm.

Figure 7: Normalised fatigue stress versus number of cycles to failure for the different orientations of the NCFC.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, it was discussed how the biaxial non crimp fabric composite under study behaves under different off-axis orientations. For small misorientations of only a few degrees, a small influence on the static stiffness was noted. A marked decrease in static strength was observed, however, which was found to be dependent on the width of the test sample. From extrapolation of the results for different sample widths to an infinite width, it was concluded that the strength decrease due to a 5° misorientation was approximately 20 %. Indications for an effect of the sample width were also found in the fatigue tests, where for wider samples the fatigue life curve seems to become less steep.

For larger off-axis angles, the influence of the orientation on the stiffness of the samples was found to correspond to the predictions of the classical laminate theory. The strength decreased sharply for an off-axis orientation of 15°, and was very similar for 30° and 45° oriented samples. The observed damage initiation stress differed more from the predicted first ply failure, especially for large off-axis angles. This difference was attributed to the non-linearity of the matrix material.

The fatigue life curves for the different orientations were constructed and it was found that the orientation has a similar effect on the fatigue strength as on the static strength. Normalisation of the fatigue life curves with respect to the static strength effectively removed the orientation dependence.

References

1. Hashin, Z. and A. Rotem. "A fatigue failure criterion for fiber-reinforced materials". *Journal of composite materials*, 1973. 7: p. 448-464.
2. Varvani-Farahani, A., H. Haftchenari, and M. Panbechi. "An energy-based fatigue damage parameter for off-axis unidirectional FRP composites". *Composite Structures*, 2007. 79(3): p. 381-389.
3. Kawai, M., S. Yajima, A. Hachinohe, and Y. Takano. "Off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber-reinforced composites at room and high temperatures". *J Compos Mater*, 2001. 35 (76): p. 545–576.
4. Kawai, M. and T. Taniguchi. "Off-axis fatigue behavior of plain weave carbon/epoxy fabric laminates at room and high temperatures and its mechanical modeling". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2006. 37(2): p. 243-256.
5. Kawai, M. and N. Honda. "off-axis fatigue behavior of a carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminate and predictions considering inelasticity and in situ strength of embedded plies". *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2008. 30: p. 1743-1755.